

Giving Egg White Pudding on Albumin Levels in Post-Laparotomy Surgery Patients with Hypoalbuminemia

Nungky Desicha*¹, Endang Widajati², Dr. Annasari Mustafa³, I Nengah Tanu Komalyana⁴

¹Nutrition Students & Banyuwangi

^{2,3,4}Nutrition Lecture & Malang

ABSTRACT

Digestive laparotomy surgery patients require special nutritional care to maintain albumin levels. Especially in cases of laparotomy with hypoalbuminemia which affects the ability to consume food adequately. Hypoalbuminemia can be overcome by administering intravenous albumin and a high-albumin diet such as egg white. Albumin is given to accelerate wound healing and treat severe blood flow disorders (shock) due to injury. To determine the standardized nutritional care procedures for post-laparotomy surgery patients with hypoalbuminemia by implementing egg pudding interludes to increase albumin levels.

A case study was conducted in April 2025 on patients after being discharged from the Blambangan Banyuwangi Regional Hospital. The data collection method was observation for 14 days on aspects of intake, physical/clinical, anthropometry and biochemistry. Researchers also conducted a literature study to complete and review the data. After nutritional intervention, the patient's physical/clinical complaints began to decrease, Albumin levels gradually increased, and the patient's intake gradually increased although it had not reached the target.

KEYWORDS: egg white pudding; laparotomy; hypoalbuminemia

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
15 September 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

I. INTRODUCTION

Hypoalbuminemia is a blood albumin level below normal, this condition can occur in malnutrition, systemic disease, malignancy and hypermetabolism due to infection, medical or surgical procedures. High protein foods can increase and maintain albumin levels and minimize the possibility of decreased albumin levels. Protein needs need to be increased to 2 grams / kg body weight 1 so that nutritional needs are met. Increasing albumin levels in the blood can be done in several ways, including providing high-protein Oral Supplements in the form of 2 egg whites. The addition of egg whites either in processed form or in extract form is given during the main meal and snacks can be applied.

Hospital malnutrition data shows that 40-50% of patients experience hypoalbuminemia or are at risk of hypoalbuminemia, 12% of whom have severe hypoalbuminemia, and the length of hospitalization of patients with hospital malnutrition is 90% longer than patients with good nutrition. In addition to malnutrition, hypoalbuminemia often occurs in patients with kidney

disorders, chronic liver disorders, burns, and cancer/malignancy, pregnancy, congestive heart failure, and malabsorption syndrome. Hypoalbuminemia reflects an inadequate supply of amino acids from protein, thus disrupting the synthesis of albumin and other proteins by the liver. In general, in hospitals, patient albumin levels can be increased by administering intravenous albumin fluids and providing high-protein food intake. However, there are several difficulties in administering oral albumin in increasing blood albumin levels in patients with hypoalbuminemia. In patients with digestive tract disorders, there is impaired absorption of albumin so that oral albumin cannot be given.

The level of leftover food in hospital patients is very high and must be addressed, in addition, patients with post-laparotomy surgery with hypoalbuminemia greatly affect intake factors such as nausea, surgical wound pain and gastrointestinal disorders. In hypoalbuminemia conditions, there will be disruption to physiological processes in the body, especially in patients who are seriously ill so that it

Giving Egg White Pudding on Albumin Levels in Post-Laparotomy Surgery Patients with Hypoalbuminemia

interferes with or inhibits the healing and recovery process. There is a relationship between low albumin levels and an increased risk of 123 Ferry Erdani et al. / Journal of Medical Science Vol. 2 No. 2, October 2021 infectious complications, long wound healing time, long hospitalization, high mortality rates in hospitalized patients, both patients who did not undergo surgery and patients who underwent surgery (Delgado et al., 2003).

Previous studies have shown that giving 15 g/day of egg white to patients with end-stage renal failure increases serum albumin levels higher than with a conventional diet for 3-6 months. A 2015 study at Prof. Dr. Margono Soekarjo Hospital showed that giving egg white juice extract for 10 days increased serum albumin levels by an average of 1.13 g/dL in tuberculosis patients with hypoalbuminemia. Providing an adequate diet that is appropriate to the condition and severity of the disease will reduce complications of the disease and decrease the general condition of the patient. So far, the provision of extra egg white in hospitals has been in the form of side dishes so that the acceptability is lacking and causes a lot of food waste. In this study, egg white is given in the form of a refreshing pudding so that it will increase the acceptability of the patient's protein intake and have an impact on increasing the patient's albumin levels. This study aims to determine the effect of giving extra egg white pudding on increasing albumin levels in patients with hypoalbuminemia.

II. METHOD

A case study was conducted in April 2025 on patients after being discharged from inpatient care at BLAMBANGAN Regional Hospital. Sample selection was carried out by hospital nutritionists and clinical instructors by considering case criteria. The method used for data collection was observation for 10 days in the intake domain using the comstock method, the physical domain using interviews, the anthropometric domain using body weight measurements, and the biochemical domain using patient medical records. In addition, a literature study was also conducted to complete the data needed and to review the data obtained. The intervention was carried out by providing egg white pudding as a snack. The target achievement in the intake aspect is the fulfillment of patient nutritional intake by $\geq 80\%$.

III. CASE AND DISCUSSION

In this case study, a 60-year-old female patient was admitted to the hospital on February 17, 2025 with a diagnosis of Attention to Ileostomy status post-operative laparotomy exploration repair ileum. The patient has been declared cured and was allowed to leave the hospital on February 25, 2025. The patient's wound condition was also stated to be improving. During observation, the patient complained of pain in the surgical wound, coughing up phlegm for 2 days, abdominal pain and cramps, and sometimes nausea. During the illness, the patient experienced

a weight loss of around 5 kg. The patient has a history of pulmonary tuberculosis 6 years ago and has undergone 6 months of complete TB treatment. It is known that the patient is a farmer who has a habit of eating 3 times a day but is not balanced and the variety of food is not diverse. The animal side dishes that are usually consumed are chicken and sea fish every day, vegetable side dishes are rarely consumed 1-2 / week, namely tempeh. The patient does not like beef. Vegetables that are often consumed are clear moringa and spinach soup. Fruits that are often consumed are bananas and papaya. The patient likes to drink black coffee 1.250ml/day, herbal medicine for aches and pains 1x/month, herbal medicine boiled coconut leaves 200cc 1x/month and drink sweet tea 250 ml/day and boiled sweet potatoes, cassava 2-3x/day.

In this case, the patient's age, which has entered the early elderly category and unbalanced eating habits are risk factors for malnutrition. The immune response after vaccination varies from individual to individual. Age is one of the important factors in the difference in immune response after vaccination. The production of T lymphocytes and the formation of B lymphocytes decrease with age so that the immune response after vaccination may be lower in old age (Uysal et al., 2022) [1]. The reason is because the immune response in older individuals tends to be lower than that in younger individuals, and also tends to be lower than that in female individuals, as observed in a study by Arora et al., (2022) [2].

Nutrition has been known to play an important role in the wound healing process, where in malnutrition there will be obstacles in the normal process of wound healing. Research by Sinha et al. (2015) [3] that 65% of patients with pre-operative hypoalbuminemia, anemia, malnutrition, respiratory tract disease and emergency surgery experienced burst abdomen. The occurrence of burst abdomen can be reduced post-operatively by improving the nutritional status of patients and providing aseptic measures and improving surgical techniques. Burst abdomen can cause metabolic disorders and infections that are at risk of sepsis and even organ failure which can cause death. Poor nutritional status is caused by inadequate food intake due to decreased appetite and increased nutritional needs in hypermetabolic conditions associated with surgery. Low serum albumin values will affect the healing process due to inadequate intake and due to increased inflammatory responses so that albumin synthesis is inadequate.

Modified egg white pudding is a snack made from egg white and food ingredients that have high biological value in one portion. Pudding is made as an alternative food given to hypoalbumin patients with oral therapy. Egg white is an animal protein ingredient that contains the most ovalbumin. Egg white contains 10.5 grams of protein/100 grams of egg white and 95% of which is albumin 9.83 grams. Egg white also increases albumin and hemoglobin levels in the blood (Syamsiatun & Siswati, 2015) [4].

Giving Egg White Pudding on Albumin Levels in Post-Laparotomy Surgery Patients with Hypoalbuminemia

The nutritional content of extra egg white pudding for one serving of one meal for each snack has 108.4 kcal. The percentage of energy and nutrient intake in snacks is around 10% of the needs. This is in accordance with Alamtsier (2005) [5]. The ideal percentage of snacks for daily needs is around 10-15% of the total daily calorie needs, both for morning and afternoon snacks.

In the biochemical examination results (Table 1), the leukocyte value shows a number above the standard value indicating an infection due to inflammation. In addition, the process of infection or acute inflammation also occurs in patients which can be seen from the high WBC or white blood cell value and low albumin (NiaGita.RK & Mardina, 2019) [6]. In addition to being a marker of inflammation, low albumin values are also known to be an indication of protein energy deficiency (Pratiwi, 2020) [7].

Based on the assessment that has been carried out, it was concluded that: (1) The patient's energy and nutrient intake is less than the needs related to nausea, abdominal pain, and cramps, which is characterized by energy, protein, and carbohydrate intake less than the needs. (2) There is an increase in the patient's protein needs related to inflammation

of the surgical wound, which is characterized by a decrease in albumin values. (3) The patient's inappropriate diet is related to unpreparedness to implement a diet characterized by unbalanced and less diverse eating habits.

Based on the nutritional diagnosis above, nutritional intervention is given by providing food according to the patient's needs and conditions. The interventions given aim to reduce leukocyte levels, increase albumin levels, increase hemoglobin levels and meet the patient's energy and nutritional needs to maintain normal nutritional status. Calculation of patient energy needs is done using the Mifflin-St Jeor formula by considering physical activity factors and stress factors, the patient's energy needs are 2011.2 kcal. The diet given is the TETP Diet 2100 kcal with energy from protein, fat, and carbohydrates respectively 20%, 25%, and 55%. The diet takes into account food ingredients that are high in amino acids from easily digestible proteins, iron from heme proteins. The diet is given in the form of regular food with oral administration. The frequency of diet is 10 times a day, which is divided into 3 main meals and 2 egg white pudding snacks. The patient's food intake is expected to meet the target of at least 80% of the total needs.

i. Nutritional Content of Egg White Pudding per serving

Nutrients	Nutritional content
Energy (kcal)	108.4
Protein (grams)	5
Fat (grams)	2
Carbohydrates (grams)	18
Fiber (milligrams)	1

Based on the results of monitoring and evaluation, the patient's energy intake increased (Table 2). The patient's energy intake for 10 days met the consumption level, which was normal, on the third to fifth day of monitoring the patient complied with the energy and nutrient intake with no leftover food, the consumption level met the range of 110-115% of the needs. The provision of the 2100 kcal TETP Diet was continued considering that there were no complaints related to the form and type of diet or other complaints that required a change in diet. On the sixth to tenth day, the patient's energy intake increased to 1447 kcal or around 76.2% of the

needs. On the third day, the patient's energy intake decreased to 97%, 84.2%, 91%, 91%, 97% of the needs. Likewise, the intake of other macronutrients such as protein, fat and carbohydrates decreased every day. The patient's leftover food (Table 3) especially at each meal break with egg white pudding from the sixth to the tenth day gradually decreased and left 50% leftover food. Despite the decrease, the patient's food intake for ten days of energy and protein reached the normal category, but fat and carbohydrates were in the mild deficit category. This is related to the patient starting to get bored and nauseous when consuming egg white pudding.

ii. Results of Interpretation of Patient Examination

Check	Results	Standard Value	Description
Food Recall			
Energy	492,4 kcal	2011,2 kcal	24,4 % Severe level deficit
Protein	37,1 grams	100,5 grams	36,9 % Severe level deficit
Fat	0,2 grams	55,8 grams	0,5 % Severe level

Giving Egg White Pudding on Albumin Levels in Post-Laparotomy Surgery Patients with Hypoalbuminemia

			deficit
Carbohydrates	24,4 grams	276,5 grams	9,1 % Severe level deficit
Antropometri			
Height (estimated) with ulna length	168,7 cm	168 cm	Normal
Body Weight (Estimated) with %LILA	64 kg	61 Kg	Normal nutritional status
Check	Results	Standard Value	Description
Biochemistry			
Leukocytes	13,0	3,8-10,6	High
Lymphocytes	5,2	20-40	Low
Hemoglobin	14,6	13,2-18	Normal
Platelets	263	150-440	Normal
Albumin	3,2	3,6-4,8	Low
Chloride	95,9	95,8	Low
Magnesium	0,43	0,73-1.06	Low
Physical/Clinical			
Surgical wound pain	there is	no there is	not normal
nausea	there is	no there is	not normal
Flatus	there is	there is	Normal
Cough	no there is	no there is	Normal
Blood Pressure	120/80 mmHg	120/80 mmHg	Normal
Pulse	76 x/menit	75-115 x/menit	Normal
Respiratory Rate	20 x/menit	22-34 x/menit	Normal
Temperature	36.3 °C	36-37.5 °C	Normal

Giving Egg White Pudding on Albumin Levels in Post-Laparotomy Surgery Patients with Hypoalbuminemia

iii. Results of Monitoring and Evaluation of Patient Food Remains

Date	Description	Staple Food	Animal Side	Side Dishes	Vegetable	Snacks
26/4/ 2025 Day- 1	Breakfast	0	0	-	0	0
	Lunch	0	0	-	0	0
	Dinner	0	0	0	0	-
	Average (%)	0	0	0	0	0
27/4/ 2025 Day- 2	Breakfast	0	0	0	0	0
	Lunch	0	0	0	0	0
	Dinner	0	0	0	0	-
	Average (%)	0	0	0	0	0
28/4/ 2025 Day - 3	Breakfast	0	0	0	0	0
	Lunch	0	0	-	0	0
	Dinner	0	0	-	0	-
	Average (%)	0	0	0	0	0
29/4/ 2025 Day - 4	Breakfast	0	0	50%	0	0
	Lunch	0	0	10%	0	0
	Dinner	0	0	-	0	-
	Average (%)	0	0	30	0	0
30/4/ 2025 Day - 5	Breakfast	0	0	-	0	0
	Lunch	0	0	20%	0	0
	Dinner	0	0	10%	0	-
	Average (%)	0	0	15	0	0
01/5/ 2025 Day - 6	Breakfast	0	0	0	0	0
	Lunch	0	0	0	0	0
	Dinner	0	0	0	0	-
	Average (%)	0	0	0	0	0
02/5/ 2025 Day - 7	Breakfast	50	50	-	10	25
	Lunch	-	10	25	20	50
	Dinner	20	10	25	20	-
	Average (%)	35	23,3	25	16,6	37,5
03/5/ 2025 Day - 8	Breakfast	10	25	50	50	50
	Lunch	25	25	0	10	50
	Dinner	25	0	-	10	-
	Average (%)	20	25	50	23,3	50
04/5/ 2025 Day - 9	Breakfast	0	25	25	25	25
	Lunch	50	25	25	25	50
	Dinner	25	10	-	25	-
	Average (%)	25	20	25	25	37,5
05/5/ 2025 Day - 10	Breakfast	25	25	10	10	25
	Lunch	25	25	50	10	25
	Dinner	0	25	-	0	-
	Average (%)	16,6	25	30	6,6	25

Giving Egg White Pudding on Albumin Levels in Post-Laparotomy Surgery Patients with Hypoalbuminemia

Date	Observation	Energy (kcal)	Protein (grams)	Fat (grams)	Carbohydrate (grams)
26/4/2025 Day ke-1	Intake	2079,3	83,3	49	218,2
	Requirements	2011,2	100,5	55,8	276,5
	Consumption Level (%)	104	83	88	79
27/4/2025 Day ke-2	Intake	2113,3	107,3	47,2	199,4
	Requirements	2011,2	100,5	55,8	276,5
	Consumption Level (%)	105,1	107	84,5	72
28/4/2025 Day ke-3	Intake	2245,3	93,3	37,4	235,1
	Requirements	2011,2	100,5	55,8	276,5
	Consumption Level (%)	111,6	93	67	85
29/4/2025 Day ke-4	Intake	2283,9	114,1	52,9	258,1
	Requirements	2011,2	100,5	55,8	276,5
	Consumption Level (%)	113,5	113,5	94,8	93,3
30/4/2025 Day ke-5	Intake	2290,3	114,8	54,3	277,7
	Requirements	2011,2	100,5	55,8	276,5
	Consumption Level (%)	114	114,2	97,3	100,4
01/5/2025 Day ke-6	Intake	1944,4	98,1	49,69	226,4
	Requirements	2011,2	100,5	55,8	276,5
	Consumption Level (%)	97	98	89	82
02/5/2025 Day ke-7	Intake	1693	78,5	30,39	141,4
	Requirements	2011,2	100,5	55,8	276,5
	Consumption Level (%)	84,2	78	54,4	51
03/5/2025 Day ke-8	Intake	1828	92,1	34,89	161,4
	Requirements	2011,2	100,5	55,8	276,5
	Consumption Level (%)	91	92	62,5	58,4
04/5/2025 Day ke-9	Intake	1833	95,2	49,3	177,4
	Requirements	2011,2	100,5	55,8	276,5
	Consumption Level (%)	91,1	95	88	64
05/5/2025 Day	Intake	1944	90,2	57	184,7
	Requirements	2011,2	100,5	55,8	276,5
	Consumption	97	90	102	66,8

Giving Egg White Pudding on Albumin Levels in Post-Laparotomy Surgery Patients with Hypoalbuminemia

ke-10	Level (%)				
Rata-rata asupan	2025,45	96,69	46,207	207,98	
% rata-rata asupan	100,85	91,56	82,75	75,19	

iv. Results of Monitoring and Evaluation of Patient Food Intake for 10 Days

Biochemical monitoring and evaluation were conducted by looking at the patient's electronic medical records. Based on the results of monitoring and evaluation (Table 5), it was found that there was no change in the patient's Albumin. The absence of change is likely due to the provision of intervention, namely egg white pudding, not being consumed regularly for two weeks. This is in line with the remaining food of the patient's egg white pudding since the observation on the 6th day of the remaining food 25%. In addition, a

study by Siswati, T and Syamsiyatun, N (2016) [8] stated that the half-life of albumin in plasma ranges from 8-20 days so that it takes at least 7-10 days to reach normal plasma albumin levels again. Research at Prof. Dr. Margono Soekarjo Hospital showed that administration of egg white extract for 10 days increased serum albumin levels by an average of 1.13 g/dL in tuberculosis patients with hypoalbuminemia. During the monitoring and evaluation of intake, the patient also experienced nausea and boredom with the provision of egg white pudding intervention.

v. Results of Biochemical Monitoring and Evaluation

Parameters	3 Feb 2025	18 april 2025	25 april 2025	29 april 2025
Albumin	2,6 g/dl	3,0 g/dl	3,2 g/dl	3,2 g/dl

Anthropometric monitoring and evaluation were carried out by weighing. Based on the results of monitoring and evaluation (Table 6), the patient experienced weight gain in

the last week after leaving the hospital. This shows that the goal of providing a diet to maintain normal nutritional status has been achieved.

vi. Results of Anthropometric Monitoring and Evaluation

Parameters	18 april 2025	25 april 2025	29 april 2025
Weight (kg)	61	62	62

Physical/clinical monitoring and evaluation were also conducted by looking at the oxymetry device and interviewing the patient. Based on the results of monitoring and evaluation (Table 7), it was found that complaints of cough, chest pain, shortness of breath, nausea, and abdominal

pain and cramps in patients decreased. The patient's respiratory rate decreased and was classified as normal on April 26, 2025, but increased again the following day. This is related to the ongoing complaints of shortness of breath.

vii. Results of Physical/Clinical Monitoring and Evaluation

Parameters	26/4/2025 Day ke-1	29/4/2025 Day ke-4	03/5/2025 Day ke-8
Cough	++ (sedang)	- (no there is)	+ (light)
Pain	- (no there is)	- (no there is)	+ (light)
Shortness of breath	- (no there is)	- (no there is)	- (no there is)
Nausea	- (no there is)	++ (moderate)	+ (light)
Stomach pain and cramps	- (no there is)	- (no there is)	+ (light)
Blood pressure	120/80 mmHg	130/80 mmHg	130/80 mmHg
Respiratory rate	20x/menit	21x/menit	21x/menit
Temperature	36 ⁰ C	36 ⁰ C	36 ⁰ C
Heart rate	96x/menit	96x/menit	96x/menit

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on monitoring and evaluation for ten days, the patient's food intake gradually increased insignificantly, but the food intake reached the target consumption level of the normal category. The results of the patient's albumin examination showed no change. In the ten days, the patient's weight changed. The results of the patient's physical/clinical examination showed that the patient's complaints of coughing, pain from surgical wounds, nausea, abdominal pain, and cramps decreased.

Based on the results of this study, egg white-based pudding products are considered to have specific nutritional content and are more acceptable to panelists when compared to regular pudding products. In addition, the pudding from this study has a high albumin content that is not inferior to regular pudding.

V. RECOMMENDATION

For further researchers with similar cases, they should pay attention to adding types and forms of interventions in the form of food snacks that will be given to patients by considering the patient's condition so that they can be consumed according to the patient's needs.

It is therefore recommended that Blambangan Regional Hospital provide nutritional support in the form of egg white pudding to post-surgery patients with hypoalbumin accompanied by providing information to patients about the benefits of the nutritional support provided so that patient acceptance of the nutritional support can be increased, carry out further coordination between medical personnel in the hospital, especially those treating surgical patients with hypoalbumin, and make stricter regulations regarding the patient visit system. Further research is needed on nutritional support by controlling certain factors, for example, patients who receive nutritional support are not given food or drinks that use raw materials like those used in the nutritional support products provided.

REFERENCES

- I. HULME, K. D., GALLO, L. A., & SHORT, K. R. (2017). INFLUENZA VIRUS AND GLYCEMIC VARIABILITY IN DIABETES: A KILLER COMBINATION? *FRONTIERS IN MICROBIOLOGY*, 8(MAY). [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.3389/FMICB.2017.00861](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.00861)
- II. KALRA, S., & SHARMA, S. K. (2018). DIABETES IN THE ELDERLY. *DIABETES THERAPY*, 9(2), 493–500.
- III. NIAGITA.RK, C. R., & MARDINA, V. (2019). EXAMINATION OF LEUKOCYTE COUNT, ERYTHROCYTE SEDIMENTATION RATE AND ACID-FAST BACTERIA (AFB) IN PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS PATIENTS AT LANGSA HOSPITAL. *JURNAL BIOLOGICA SAMUDRA*, 1(2), 6 15
- IV. JUWITA, D. 2021. THE EFFECT OF ADDING FRUIT JUICE TO EGG WHITE PUDDING AS AN ALTERNATIVE HIGH ALBUMIN FOOD AT RADEN MATTATHER JAMBI REGIONAL HOSPITAL. (ONLINE), [HTTPS://PUSTAKA.POLTEKKES-PDG.AC.ID/INDEX.PHP?P=FSTREAM-PDF&FID=3300&BID=8778](https://pustaka.poltekkes-pdg.ac.id/index.php?p=fstream-pdf&fid=3300&bid=8778). ACCESSED JUNE 29, 2025
- V. SYAMSIYATUN, N.H., & SISWATI, T. (2015). GIVING EGG WHITE JUICE EXTRACT TO ALBUMIN AND Hb LEVELS IN HYPOALBUMINEMIA PATIENTS. *JURNAL INDONESIA*, 12(2), 54.
- VI. PRATIWI, A. T. (2020). POTENTIAL OF SNAKEHEAD FISH (*OPHIOCEPHALUS STRATIUS*) TO INCREASE ALBUMIN LEVELS IN HYPOALBUMINEMIA PATIENTS. *JIMKI: INDONESIAN MEDICAL STUDENT SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL*, 8(3), 204 210. [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.53366/JIMKI.V8I3.25](https://doi.org/10.53366/jimki.v8i3.25).
- VII. SISWATI, T AND SYAMSIYATUN, N (2016). GIVING EGG WHITE JUICE EXTRACT TO ALBUMIN AND Hb LEVELS IN PATIENTS WITH HYPOALBUMINEMIA. (ONLINE), [HTTPS://PDFS.SEMANTICSCHOLAR.ORG/19B6/36767019E43ACC9A447AA4E630A79D41E32E.PDF](https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/19b6/36767019e43acc9a447aa4e630a79d41e32e.pdf). ACCESSED ON APRIL 18, 2025.